

Fundamentals of a New Research Method

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this work is to give a foundation, as an auxiliary or complementary research method, to the search for an adequate explanation of real phenomena or not, elaborated from the perspective of the observer. There are several antecedents from philosophy and from science, which justify this way of analyzing the biological, psychic and sociocultural reality of man. By using the same tool, we are approached the scientific method and explained the structure of theory and research models. We use transcurssive logic, as we call the method we have developed, to characterize a "semantic-relational transform." That is, as the temporal evolution of a relational structure allowing the delimitation of the fundamental elements that intervene any original approach made of the real dynamics. Then, in the case of scientific problems, it can be applied to them; the rigorous process of analysis, organization of available material, ordering, and criticism of the ideas required by the current methodology so that what is obtained is valid scientific knowledge. In this way, guidelines are given to favor both creativity and discovery, by simultaneously opposing the observer to the observed, through quantitative and qualitative transformations. Numerous examples of successful application are provided in different areas of human knowledge. From all of the above arise the methodological foundations that are summarized as: a) Find the fundamental elements that characterize a phenomenon. b) Depending on a pair of conflicting attributions, assign them an operative identity; c) With the fundamental elements and the transformations that link them, form an algebraic group of permutation, which acts as a "basic dynamic pattern" while at the same time ensuring the appropriate methodological adjustment, and d) Any transformation that does not belong to the "basic pattern" can be used to transfer to a new system, representative of another phenomenon, the fundamental aspects of known systems so that once they conform to the generic pattern, we can explain the new phenomenon.

Keyword: scientific theory and explanation, scientific method, methodological foundation, creativity, transcurssive logic.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

On the banks of the Rhine, a beautiful castle had been standing for centuries. In the cellar of the castle, an intricate network of webbing had been constructed by industrious spiders who lived there. One day a strong wind sprang up and destroyed the web. Frantically the spiders worked to repair the damage. They thought it was their webbing that was holding up the castle.
Morris Kline, 1980, p. 277.

Philosophy and Science, as diverse branches of knowledge, harbor a logic that sustains them and gives the possibility that the first justifies the second. However, this is not the only coincidence or relationship since both in addition to trying to found a set of statements about reality, constitute a method.

The methodological value provided by both philosophy and science is multifaceted. Basing an argument to reach the truth is proper to philosophize. While to elaborate a hypothesis on a real phenomenon, in order to look for an element with what to measure and to elaborate an experiment that allows corroborating the hypothesis, it is in itself a scientific task. Despite the apparent methodological differences, both pursue a common goal to explain the facts.

The nature of this explanation, although it is show in different ways according to the perspective from which it is analyzed, actually obeys a composition of similar basic elements. In this paper, we will try to base a useful methodology to approach the investigation of real phenomena, in search of an adequate explanation of them, elaborated from the perspective of the observer.

2.0 EXPLANATION

Explanation is not so much to clear the facts of what prevents us from understanding, as an attempt to make them compatible with the beliefs, principles, and convictions that make up our knowledge. Given that reality manifests itself to us as a continuous, indefinable and persistent process, explaining its facts will require making at least some of its fundamental aspects ostensible. Following the proposal by Aristotle (2007, Book II, Chapter 3 - The causes) we will start from the mere apprehension of the "what" to reach the first cause, to true knowledge, to an explanation of "why" the phenomenon is analyzed.

We could assimilate a real phenomenon, by using a day-to-day frame of reference to the Cartesian system that we use to represent space. In its three dimensions, we will have three basic aspects that will allow us to characterize any phenomenon: "what" makes it manifest, "how" it does it and "when" it occurs.

Fig. 1. Explanation of a phenomenon

To achieve our goal, we will turn to the argumentative options of the basic modes of reasoning provided by Philosophy (Aristotle, 2004), Logic (Peirce, 1878) and Science (Samaja, 2005). On the other hand, we will take with a certain license and as a guide, the nomological-deductive model of Carl G. Hempel (1965).

In Figure 1, we see a subject ($S = 1D$) observing the "what" of any phenomenon ($1D$). This observation is not made impartially but is conditioned by a "pattern" (Samaja, 2005, p.106) taken by analogy, as an "implicit universal individual" (Hegel, 1982, T.II, p. 392). This way of "observing" will allow the observer, to extract from the "analogous rule" (known), the rule of the analogate (unknown) phenomenon. The "analogous rule" does not derive from observation itself, but from praxis. By an abductive mechanism (rule (pattern) + result \rightarrow case), which contributes on existence and actuality, we can achieve the "how", that is, describe the observed phenomenon, thus obtaining the antecedent event demanded by the nomological-deductive model, as its explanandum or object ($O = 2D$) of the observation (Hempel, 1965, p.246).

An inductive mechanism (result + case \rightarrow rule) that tells us about generality allows us to predict the phenomenon ("when"). That is, to assign a general law, which is none other than the one provided by the "pattern", and so, based on experience (in a habit or custom) (Hume, 1894, p.44) to expect in the future a succession of events similar to those that appeared in the past, in similar situations. We have reached the third dimension ($3D$) that characterizes our phenomenon, or the "general law" that in appearance, directly relates the observer subject and the observed object ($V = 3D$).

Finally, a deductive mechanism (case + rule \rightarrow conclusion) that promotes possibility and potentiality allows us to arrive at an explanation of the phenomenon that we are analyzing. The explanation obtained is independent of both the observer and the observed phenomenon, that is why it is "dimensionless" ($\nabla = 0D$). One's "absence" in the Cartesian system, in reality, tells us that it is projected in a fourth dimension ($4D =$ coordinate axis inscribed in the figure). It represents an indirect (or qualitative) relationship between the observer and the observed, so it is impossible to detect it.

3.0 UNIVERSAL PATTERN

In the previous point, we have verified that it is possible to move from the "what" to the Aristotelian "why" of a phenomenon, taking as a guide a pattern that provides the general law from which, by deduction, arise a conclusion, an explanation or the cause (s) determinant (s) of the phenomenon that we are analyzing. This was possible by integrating inductive and deductive reasoning with reasoning by analogy (abduction). Such an elaboration would cease to be pure conjecture if we were able to find as a pattern an "implicit universal individual," inductively providing a general law based on a "sample" that encompasses the entire universe (ideal induction). In this way, it is possible to avoid the criteria of the critical approach that Hempel makes about induction, in his logical theory of confirmation (Hempel, 1965, p.5)

Thus, we propose a complementary research method. The main foundation of this proposal lies in having discovered that the interrelationships maintained between the fundamental aspects that define any phenomenon (real or not), constitute a "universal pattern" based on a group of transformations. An invariant that respects the principle of symmetry and, therefore, adheres to the principle of "uniformity of nature" elaborated by J. S. Mill (1882, p.400), as the foundation of induction. Principle confirmed by Emmy Noether (1915-1918) when he demonstrated the conservation of natural laws over time, by relating in his theorem, the symmetry of a system with quantities that are conserved.

The first outline of a possible universal pattern emerges when reading the "Poetics" of Aristotle.

"I explain the metaphor by analogy as what can happen when, of four things, the second remains in the same relation to the first as the fourth to the third; then you can talk about

the fourth instead of the second, and the second instead of the fourth." (Aristotle, 2011, Chapter XXI, 1457b).

In symbols, it would be $2 : 1 :: 4 : 3$. That is, the second is to the first as the fourth is to the third. This, in addition to expressing two oppositions by complementarity, represents the germ of all Aristotelian logic.

It is curious, but the DNA molecule, the basis of the genetic code and life, turned out to be structured in the same way. Figure 2 shows the arrangement of its nitrogenous bases (cytosine, guanine, adenine, thymine) in opposite pairs. Both the decimal codes (which give their order or "relational valence") and the binary codes (which identify the pairs of opposite and complementary bases) assigned, have a solid foundation. The former is based on their electrochemical structure (number of nitrogen atoms with sp^2 hybrid orbitals). While the seconds depend on the chemical structure (presence or absence of different heterocyclic rings).

Fig. 2 DNA Molecule (Salatino, 2009)

The assignment of binary codes to the basic components of the DNA molecule allowed us to demonstrate that this composition of abstract elements conforms, structurally, a permutation group or Galois group. From the functional point of view it also represents a "connection" of Galois, that is, the opposition of two aspects through another opposition.

"Different interests that lead to different procedures can gather evidence that can then materialize in an empirically grounded worldview." (Feyerabend, 2001, p.184)

The aphorism of Van Fraassen (1989) "Similar problems have similar solutions", and the fact that DNA is a "universal pattern", a series of practical examples were taken to demonstrate the relevance of the method of searching for a basic relational pattern as part of the solution of a given problem.

4.0 GENERIC GROUP

To address the different approaches, to which we should find a solution or an explanation, a tool based on a generic Galois group was built.

Isolating the essential or relevant structure of a phenomenon is equivalent to defining a group of transformations that, once applied, leave the problem, essentially, in the same situation from where it started (invariance). These transformations are the "symmetries" of the problem (Noether, 1918) With the essential aspects formed a group (a logical-structural arrangement) which we call PAU (Universal Autonomous Pattern), and the solution consists of a rule (a function) that depends only on those basic parameters (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Generic Group

In the previous figure we see two essential aspects of any phenomenon (A and B) and the relationships that they keep with each other through two transformations: a superficial or apparent (V) and another hidden or profound (∇). The way we have to identify each of these elements is through the individualization of some characteristic that is specific to each essential aspect (α and β). According to the resulting binary codes, A is identified as having the characteristic β , but not the α . On the contrary, B is identified as having the characteristic α , but not the β . This is telling us that A and B are opposites concerning the characteristics α and β , which are mutually exclusive. The transformations are distinguished because, the superficial (V) has both characteristics (α and β) of the aspects it relates (A and B), is what we call co-presence or organization, or what is evidenced in any phenomenon that is being observed.

The profound transformation (∇), on the other hand, shows a total absence of the characteristics that identify the aspects it relates (co-absence or disorganization). As we can see, as with the essential aspects (A and B), here the transformations V and ∇ are opposite. Both pairs are also complementary, since added give the apparent unit (11), which is nothing but the evident or superficial transformation (the organization). It is thus formed an opposition mediated by another opposition (Galois connection).

In the scheme of the figure, it is observed that between A and B there exists, in addition to the direct relationship, mediated by a transformation that we have described, an indirect relation between them shared by the two cycles that have been formed. A superficial one dextro-rotated (in the clockwise direction) that represents the symmetries of rotation of the system and constitutes the "objective or quantitative pole", and a deep one of left-handed rotation (in the anti-clockwise direction) as an evidence of reflection symmetries of our universal pattern and represents the 'subjective or qualitative pole'. The opposite turns are another way of complementarity that ensures the simultaneity in the operation of both cycles, where both the quantitative and the qualitative aspects of any real phenomenon or not must be present at the same time (heterarchy).

Finally, so that the whole system is not just an inert structure, there must be a rule or function that sets it in motion. This rule ($\oplus = \text{XOR}$) allows to 'move' superficially, to the right (quantitative or apparent transformation) each of the elements of the level to take the place of its successor in the sequence, without losing

its own identity (symmetry of rotation), until the system returns to the beginning from where it started. With the previous operation, we assume that we have reached the solution of the problem posed by the observable aspects of the phenomenon. At a deeper level, and as it could not be otherwise, the rule or function used is the opposite of the superficial one ($\odot = \text{XNOR}$ or equivalence), which allows elements of the system to be moved to the left. Here, when the system returns to the original disposition, after the successive qualitative transformations, we obtain the complete solution to the problem (reflection symmetry). In short, it is this level, that aspects that characterize a phenomenon, the determinant of what the same phenomenon, shows us in appearance. What unites the two levels is the experience that arises from having solved, sometimes, a similar problem.

The relational structure that we have used meets the characteristics that identify a permutation or Galois group. 1) Closure: the application of a composition transformation (XOR) to a pair of its evident elements produces another element that belongs to the set. 2) It has a neutral or identity element (00) such that composed with any other element it does not modify it; 3) Each element of the set has its inverse, such that composed by a transformation, they give the neutral element. 4) Associative property: all the compositions achieved through a certain transformation are independent of their grouping. 5) The closing of the conjugate: there is an opposite transformation to the composition (XNOR) that, applied to the non-evident elements, produces another element of the set.

5.0 PAUs LIBRARY

To face the analysis of a great diversity of phenomena, which we consider as if they were systems, we have several types of PAUs. These relational structures are always shaped by the same generic and fundamental elements, only varies in each type, the sequence of their relationships (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. PAUS Library

5.1 Structural PAU

This relational disposition is useful when we must analyze a system (composed of subsystems) that interacts with its immediate environment. Here, the function of the system depends, exclusively, on its relational structure. It handles the dynamics

generated by only two variables (opposite and complementary) and does so through basic binary operations (XOR (\oplus) and XNOR (\odot)). Application examples: Neurophysiology (Neuronal and cerebral functioning), Psychology (Psychic time, Psychic structure and function, Psychoanalytic theory, Subjective reality), Organic Chemistry (Bistable systems, DNA), Medicine (Immunology of pregnancy), Logic (Laws of equivalence, Dialogics), Mathematics (Theory of groups, Differential equations, Fundamental theorem of algebra, Statistics), Physics (Electromagnetism, Theory of relativity, Quantum physics, Particle physics, Automatic control, Electrical circuits), Art (Literature (tales of Borges), Painting (Escher's work), Music (language and musical composition), Creativity), Biology (Genetic code, Formation of the organs of flowers), Linguistics (Acquisition, understanding and production of natural language), Astronomy (Copernican Revolution), Economics (Quality control), Philosophy (Epistemology), Science (Scientific research, Methodology of research), etc. (Salatino, 2009, 2012, 2013, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018).

5.2 Functional PAU

It allows address systems that represent an assembly of two or more structures to alternate in their functions. It can handle two or more variables through hybrid binary operations ($\leftarrow \oplus$ / $\rightarrow \oplus$). Examples: Economics (Economic theory, Game theory, Nash equilibrium), Theory of Evolution (Adaptation, natural balance, readaptation), Philosophy (Classification of sciences, On knowledge according to Plato, Scientific research), Psychology (Behavior and conduct, psychoanalytic theory) (Salatino, 2013, 2015, 2017e)

5.3 Cyclic PAU

This PAU allows the analysis of systems where its two levels (superficial and profound) show an explicit heterarchy. That is, its dynamics are activated by a single operation or by the use of both basic operations at the same time. This way of projecting the transformations causes the golden rule of this approach to be violated: "The profound level of a PAU, always cycles in the opposite direction to the superficial level." Here, the profound level is "dragged" by the superficial level, so that a single cycle is formed. Examples: Physics (Maxwell's Law, Stepper Electric Motors, Electrical Circuits), Mathematics (Statistics, Logarithms) (Salatino, 2016, 2017).

5.4 Bicyclic PAU

The use of this PAU is convenient when the system analyzed shows a behavior that could be called "oscillatory," due to the cyclic variations that its dynamics show. However, it also allows us to study systems that show hysteresis in its different modalities. Thus, it allows describing both the tendency of a material to conserve some of its properties in the absence of the stimulus that generated it, and those systems, structurally stable, that tend to manifest discontinuity (abrupt changes in behavior) or divergence (positive feedback). It is possible to analyze systems where their current state depends on their previous history, but if the behaviors are reversed, never return to the initial state. Examples: Physics (Electromagnetism, Electrical circuits, Chemistry), Philosophy (Conceptual evolution), Psychology (Behavior and conduct), Sociology (Competitive behavior, Models of organizational change, Models of social evolution), Economy (Unemployment rate), Logic (Laws of implication), etc. (Salatino, 2017, 2018).

5.5 Hemicyclic PAU

We can use a hemicyclic PAU when our objective is not to analyze separately the elements that determine, in appearance, the functioning of a system, as we do with a structural PAU, but to try to separate appearance of reality, as in a functional PAU. But unlike the functional PAU, here the phenomenon is approached from the direct relation of its fundamental elements and not from its transformations. Therefore, the separation between appearance and reality is achieved regardless of the functional alternation to which the elements considered may be subject. Examples: Science (Methodology of research), Mathematics (Concept of limit, Derivatives), Physics (Changes of state of matter), Neurobiology (Neural action potential), Psychology (Psychic functioning), etc. (Salatino, in press).

6.0 SCIENTIFIC METHOD

The scientific method is the main producer of knowledge in science. Based on the empirical and in the measurement, it is subject to specific rules of reasoning. (Newton, 1997, p.461)

All research is defined by an 'object of study' and by a method that enables its analysis. The 'object of study' always has to do with some portion of the reality that is intended to study, since science is, in short, a way of observing reality.

The Transcursive Logic (TL), as we call the method we have developed, also constitutes a way of scrutinizing the real, but it does so from the perspective of the subject (from the observer) and not only from the obvious or apparent manifestations that it provides us the empirical. Its 'scientific' quality is reflected in the following considerations. Scientific knowledge (the product to be achieved through research) accepts two variants: the abstract (based on theories) and the

empirical (based on the facts). The scientific method, on the other hand, also admits a couple of options: validation and discovery (Samaja, 2005, p.41). Since discovery is not comparable to facts nor validation is to a theory, it is imperative to contemplate its 'logical product.' (Figure 5)

Fig. 5. PAU of scientific research

The above scheme suggests that research always consists of a combination of procedures aimed at discovering something and procedures to validate what has been discovered. Accordingly, we do not transgress the scientific norm if we used a method that adapting to the scientific knowledge we want to achieve, provide us with the necessary tools to validate what we discover (diagonal in the diagram), which would be equivalent to discovering through a theory (code 01), as occurs, for example, with theoretical physics.

7.0 ANTECEDENTS

7.1 Babylonian tablets YBC 7289 – MS 3050

The first antecedent of a relational structure similar to a PAU is found in a pair of Babylonian tablets (YBC 7289 - MS 3050) (Friberg, 2007, p 210), about 3800 years old. In the YBC 7289 tablet, with only one figure and three numbers, it shows us that the Babylonians knew that the diagonal of a square is equal to the product of the value of its side by $\sqrt{2}$. This implies that they were familiar with what we know as the Pythagorean theorem, 1200 years before the Greek mathematician was born. It also, shows that they used a sophisticated calculation method since they practiced trigonometry based on relationships, not on angles and circles. Their trigonometric tables determine two unknown reasons for a right triangle, using only a known relation.

Fig. 6. Babylon PAUs

Making use of the previous considerations, we have superimposed (Figure 6) the value of the calculation of the variables that define the diagonals of the square proposed by the Babylonians. It can be verified that they correspond to the equation $x^2 + y^2 = 1$, that is, to the Pythagorean theorem for the case of a square inscribed in a trigonometric circle, represented in the MS 3050 tablet. If we assign '0' to the negative term ($-1 / \sqrt{2}$) and '1' to the positive term ($1 / \sqrt{2}$), we obtain the binary codes that denote the aforementioned relationships. These codes are not other than those assigned to a PAU and, therefore, meet the requirements of a group. It is easy to verify that the values housed in opposite vertices are reciprocal (opposite) and complementary, since the sum of their products, in absolute values, is worth 1:

$$\begin{aligned} (\sin (45^\circ) \times \cos (45^\circ) + \sin (225^\circ) \times \cos (225^\circ) &= 1 \\ (\sin (315^\circ) \times \cos (315^\circ) + \sin (135^\circ) \times \cos (135^\circ) &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

The mathematical representations of the analyzed Babylonian tablets fulfill the requirements demanded in this work to define a PAU.

7.2 Plato

Another antecedent of our approach, we find it in the solution that Plato gives to the paradox of Zeno in the "Parmenides."

"If there is a multiplicity, the same things must be similar and unlike. It is impossible for the like to be unlike, and for the unlike to be similar. Consequently, there is no multiplicity." (2007, 127d)

The paradox is posed as a *modus tollens*. Plato, in the words of Socrates, solves it in the following way:

"If there are multiple things, since they are multiple, they must be different. In that sense, they are dissimilar [union]. But, since all of them are dissimilar, they have all the same affection - that of being dissimilar - and for that reason, they are similar [separation or selection]." (2007, 130a) (the annotations between [] are own)

It can be argued that this solution is impossible. Indeed, it is impossible if it is posed from its "conceptual content," since, in this way, we cannot distinguish "thing" from "property", nor "subject" from "predicate". But it is not, from the relationship between the "continents," where the following circumstances occur:

Fig. 7. PAU paradox of Zeno

According to Figure 7, it can be admitted according to Socrates, that "a form is a unit on the multiplicity of particular things." These interrelationships, which in the static content of an apparent system (objective reality), would lead to a "return" to infinity," in a dynamic system (subjective reality) is a return to the same place, but a time later. The record of the evolution of the structure (experience, history) of a real system through time, of its elapse.

7.3 Aristotle

Aristotle in his "Physics" provides a new antecedent of this particular framing of the real. We must bear in mind that in the Greek tradition, the word "*physiké*" did not call a special science like Galileo's, but rather it designated everything that exists in the universe: the cosmos, inert matter and living matter, represented by plants, animals, and man. From this conception, the *phýsis* becomes the great protagonist of the passing of the real, of what is and happens, and will have as a thematic target, the movement [the transformation] (De Echandía, 2007, p.9). Thus seen, Physics will be the analysis of the physical according to its empirical manifestations, and as the foundation of appearances, as well as its explanatory argument. This approach is superior to the Parmenidean duality "appearance/truth", in that it considers the diversity of sensible movements as manifestations of the nature of things ("Physics", 191a25).

The Aristotelian conception of the *phýsis*, in some way, is a platonization of the legacy of the Ionians by accepting a "real fundamental nucleus" [the deep level of the qualitative], but also admits, which makes things end up being which are, its *Eidos*, that is, its external or apparent aspect [the superficial level of the quantitative]. Thus, the form ends up being what internally configures, things and the knowledge of the *phýsis*, according to its unmistakable empirical manifestations, which makes things "express." Both aspects allow understanding the Aristotelian theory of movement. The movement, as an empirical fact, is presented according to its sensible appearances, leaving a record of its passing. Consequently, the theory must start from the experience [history of the system] and build its "sense," its knowledge, so that it agrees with the observed facts ("About the sky", 306a6).

In the Aristotelian observations, we find a high degree of coincidence with what is proposed by the Transcursive Logic (TL). In them, the fundamental elements used by the TL are displayed to define the observed reality and to try to explain its operation. Perhaps, the most important thing is to consider the "passing," as the "wadi" to follow to couple the group of transformations that demarcate the structural evolution of a system and build its history.

7.4 Felix Klein

A closer antecedent is Klein's work on groups of transformations applied to the Erlangen program and non-Euclidean geometry. To unify the geometric investigations, it was decided to determine what they have in common and in what different branches of Geometry they differ, taking as the only parameter, the familiar notion of space.

To achieve the above, the notion of "group of transformations of space" is invoked. This notion is based on the fact that the composition of any number of transformations of space always produces another transformation. A group of transformations is constituted when the set has the property that any transformation resulting from the composition of a pair of them also belongs to the set. There are transformations of space that do not alter at all the properties of the figures since they are independent of the position occupied in space, of its absolute magnitude and finally also of the sense in which its parts are arranged. The displacements in space, the transformations of similarities and those of symmetry do not alter the intrinsic properties of the figures. It is known as "main group" the set of all these transformations. The geometrical properties are not altered by the transformations of the "main group."

Klein, in 1882, showed that any surface could be represented by a portion of the plane using a polygon in which the points on the sides were properly identified. For demonstration, it was necessary not to take into account the distances (the content), and only to consider the identification of each side (the continent) to preserve the relations that they maintain between them. A square, for example, can be transformed into a bull, without the intrinsic properties of the figures have changed (Figure 8).

Fig. 8. Topological PAU

Thus, Topology emerges as a branch of Geometry, according to the Erlangen program. In effect, the topology referred to the study of the properties of surfaces that remain invariant under the action of a group of transformations (homeomorphisms). Interestingly, although Klein has not mentioned it, if we consider the points that identify the sides of the polygon (Figure 8), we see that they also form a "group", the one that identifies the fundamental elements which define the surface, and can project the transformations. That is, they form a PAU.

7.5 Emmy Noether

Inspired by the works of Hilbert and Klein, Noether through a theorem gave a solution to the elusive problem of conservation of energy in the relativistic theory. This approach ended up offering a general frame of reference that allowed us to understand the topic of the conservation of energy in physics, beyond the theory of relativity.

Emmy Noether realized that the principles of conservation of energy were related to the "groups of transformations" and to the "invariants." These last ones that were determined by her, both in the plane, as in the space, from the mathematics, imply a group of changes and something that remains fixed under the effect of those changes. This analysis of real phenomena through models reveals important properties of the phenomenon that we want to study.

Fig. 9. Algebraic PAU

Axes: $-1 = 0 - \oplus$: XOR - \odot : XNOR - \leftrightarrow / \rightsquigarrow : hybrid

In Figure 9, if we take the values of the axes $-1 = 0$, binary code can be assigned to each quadrant. This code represents the solutions, in each quadrant, to the equation proposed which coincide with the circumference. Through the usual and hybrid operations, you can "rotate" for each of the solutions. The example shows the connection that exists between formulas, shapes, equations, and figures of the plane or space, using the idea of an "algebraic invariant." This allows applying certain transformations (translations and rotations) that show the correspondence of a law of symmetry and its corresponding conservation principle with energy, with angular momentum and with linear momentum.

Through a common abstract algebraic structure, which uses only the sum and the product, one can discover the intrinsic connections underlying problems, which, appear to be different. Something, the latter, which represents almost absolutely, what is proposed by this work.

7.6 Mosterín

A final antecedent of what is proposed in this research as method comes from the contributions of Jesús Mosterín (2003), in "Concepts and Theories in Science." The author tells us (p.203) that if we want to characterize the same structure projected in different systems, we need a procedure that allows us to describe that structure. This description must be independent of the systems that carry it out. This procedure - continuous - consists in the introduction of an extension of our language through the use of mathematical notions, and especially of "conceptors" (In our case, continents). A "conceptor" is a substitute, which in some way allows one to think, in innumerable different concepts (in our case, content), corresponding to the history of countless different systems. However, all these systems have something in common: a structure.

7.6.1 Theory of a structure

Mosterín shows that in any theory appear words (particle, mass, force, etc.) that do not express concepts [content], but "conceptors" [continents – Mosterín, p. 205]. On the other hand, he argues that if a system is a model of a theory, if it expresses the corresponding structure [if it is functional], then we can substitute the "conceptors" by concepts in the theorems, thus obtaining true ideas about the system in question.

Mosterín asserts that defining a structure is the same as formulating its theory. It is necessary to specify which are "conceptors" [continents] combined to make up the axioms, and what logic determines the relation of consequence between axioms and theorems. With this we would resolve mathematically, and univocally, the structure and its theory. However, this whole complex is independent of the empirical reality of the world. The latter gives foundation the subjective approach that TL makes from the observer.

8.0 EXAMPLES

To demonstrate the relevance of the approach to reality, of the statements made by science, and even of any human manifestation, from the point of view of the observer, and under the protection of a "universal standard," we will elaborate some examples.

8.1 Theoretical structure

Fig. 10. PAU of a theory

Figure 10 shows the relational pattern formed by the fundamental aspects that characterize a theory or system of concepts according to the following proposal of Hempel, analyzed from the Transcursive Logic.

“A scientific theory might, therefore, be likened to a complex spatial network: Its terms are represented by the knots, while the threads connecting the latter correspond, in part, to the definitions and, in part, to the fundamental and derivative hypotheses included in the theory. The whole system floats, as it were, above the plane of observation and is anchored to it by rules of interpretation. These might be viewed as strings which are not part of the network but link certain points of the latter with specific places in the plane of observation. By virtue of those interpretive connections, the network can function as a scientific theory : From certain observational data, we may ascend, via an interpretive string, to some point in the theoretical network, thence proceed, via definitions and hypotheses, to other points, from which another interpretive string permits a descent to the plane of observation.” (Hempel, 1952, p. 36).

As shown in the diagram, there are aspects that depend on the observer (the theoretical concepts). There are some that depend on the phenomenon observed (the empirical concepts). There are "correspondence laws" that directly relate the previous two. Finally, there are aspects that relate the theoretical and the empirical in an indirect and unobservable way (the derived concepts). The binary codes correspond to the attached table of assignments and serve to identify and operate with each one of them when analyzing the dynamics of the system.

The theoretical concepts and empirical concepts related by the "laws of correspondence" elaborate a "model" that will be used to test a hypothesis (superficial or apparent level - green triangle). When the results obtained with the operation of the model do not coincide properly with the real phenomenon, that is, when the theory does not predict the phenomenon and therefore does not explain it, adjustments must be made. The way to adjust the model is to bring the theory closer to the facts. This is achieved through the derived concepts, which in a non-evident way (deep level of the system) and with a lower level of abstraction, contribute new definitions to the theoretical concepts that help verify the initial hypothesis.

The operability of the system is demonstrated through the Boolean operations that appear at the bottom of the previous diagram. There one can see the way in which an emulation of the

dynamics of the system is achieved. This dynamic consists of two cycles: one superficial (clockwise) and governed by XOR (\oplus) and one deep (also clockwise) managed by XNOR (\odot) or equivalence. The first iterates several times until adjustments are needed where the second is triggered, then back to the first.

In (TL) this relational pattern is known as hemicyclic PAU.

8.2 Research Model

Figure 11. PAU OF A RESEARCH MODEL

(Method of "trajectory analysis" or multiple regression - Wright, 1921, p 557)

As proposed by Diamantopoulos & Sigauw (2013, p.1), when we analyze any phenomenon through a model, we have to measure what is represented by two "constructs": the *observable variables* and the *latent variables* that are not observable. The *observable variables* "reflect" the *latent variables*. Therefore, they are also called "reflective indicators." In turn, both constructs can be *dependent* or *independent*. Now, if a variable is not influenced by or does not depend on any other variable in the model, it is an *exogenous variable*. The *exogenous variables* always act as *independent variables*. In the model the variable that is influenced by or depends on other variables, is known as an *endogenous variable*. It must be borne in mind that *endogenous variables* may affect other *endogenous variables*. Endogenous variables that affect others can act as *independent variables* or as *dependent variables*. Empirical measures (observable variables) never have a perfect validity and reliability, therefore, a "residual term" contemplating "inexplicable variations" must be included in the model. There are two types of error that must be considered. The *measurement error* (also known as "error in the variables") and the *structural error* (also known as "error in the equations").

In the previous scheme, all the described elements are registered, but, also, the dynamic aspects of the model are included. The sequence elaborated from the TL is the following: The non-observable sustenance of the whole system is the independent latent variable (v) (∇ in TL) since it does not depend on or is influenced by any other model variable. The latent dependent variable (η) and the independent observable variable (x) depend on it. On the other hand, the dependent observable variable (y) depends on the latent dependent variable. Finally, as usual, the dependent observable variable (y) depends on the independent observable variable (x). We see that y constitutes the end of both "routes" since it represents the final result of the operation of the model and what we are going to contrast with the actual phenomenon analyzed. According to the previously mentioned relations, v is doubly exogenous (00), and y is doubly endogenous (11). The

table of assignments attached to the scheme completes the identification of the variables according to their respective characteristics.

Both "routes" are justified by the binary operations (hybrid \leftrightarrow) placed on the bottom and left side of the scheme, which starts at 00 (v) and ends at 11 (y). As for the necessary adjustments for errors made in the estimates, they are recorded, the "measure," returning from the result obtained (y) to the "source" (v) carrying the corresponding correction. This is manifested by the binary operations placed on the top and right side, respectively. While, the "structural error" is nothing that can be corrected from outside the model, but from within. That is, the equations must be adjusted, those that represented by ∇ , constitute the basis of the modeling.

8.3 Matter

We will take as another example the concept of "matter." This concept, frankly elusive, we will approach from the proposal made by Aristotle and from particle physics, through the standard model. We do not intend with these examples to express value judgment regarding the scientific pertinence of these proposals. Rather it is an approach that will allow us to better understand each of the proposals, and also to certify that the method suggested by the TL can be applied to any area of knowledge, as something has already been proven throughout the work.

8.3.1 Aristotle

"The concept of matter is not a scientific concept, but a philosophical one" (Mosterín, 2003, p.121). Introduced in philosophy by Aristotle, today can serve to clarify, in part, the problems posed by particle physics.

Aristotle assumes that all things have as distinctive aspects a matter and a form, that is, they make up a system or set of elements (matter), provided with structure (form) (Figure 12).

Fig. 12. PAU of the fundamental components of the matter

We see in the previous diagram the dynamic relationships (the forms) that link, affecting, the fundamental elements that define the matter. The attached table of assignments justifies the binary codes that we have used to identify each element, or, rather, the "continent" of each one of them. For this, the different forms that the subject can adopt have been used.

Moving from one element to another is "simulated" by the logical operations \oplus (XOR) and \ominus (Equivalence), alone or combined. ($\leftarrow p / \rightarrow q$). These transformations suggest that the content changes, but not the continent of each element, which as we see in the table, there is one (a logical operator) for each transformation.

It is possible to follow the sequence of the PAU and to verify that, at least in the appearance and sometimes, in reality these transformations are fulfilled. Thus, if the water is heated it is

transformed into the air (evaporates). If that steam dries, it turns into the fire (forest fires). If the fire cools, it becomes earth (volcanic magma). If the earth gets wet, it becomes water (alluvium). There is a real way in which the water is transformed, directly, into the fire, by heating and simultaneous drying. This is what happens, for example, when water is heated to such a temperature that its molecular bonds break down. Water disappears as such and transforms into two gases: hydrogen (fuel) and oxygen (comburent), which produces fire.

8.3.2. Particle physics (Standard model)

In the 1940s, it was possible to determine experimentally that the atoms consisted of electron clouds (negatively charged particles) that orbit a compact nucleus located at its center. The nucleus, in turn, was made up of protons (positive charge) and neutrons (without charge). These particles arranged in a variable number determined the identity of the chemical element to which the atom belonged. But then it was learned that the elementary particles of the nucleus were composed of smaller particles (quarks). That there were subatomic particles that explained the "strong interaction" that holds protons and neutrons together inside the nucleus. In special situations like when a star collapses, it appears by disintegration (weak interaction), another group of subatomic particles. (Lederman & Hill, 2004, p.35). The process that destroys a star transforming it into Supernova, the β decay, constitutes a remarkable example of weak interaction, and it is where the following phenomenon occurs: $p^+ + e^- \rightarrow n^0 + \nu^0$ (proton + electron \rightarrow neutron + neutrino) (Figure 13).

Fig. 13. PAUs of the elemental forces

Figure 13 highlights the fundamental interactions that complete the standard particle model. These forces (equivalent to the Aristotelian forms) are (Figure 13, left): the electromagnetic that binds the electron to the nucleus and whose carrier is a boson that lacks mass and electrical charge: the photon (γ). The strong nuclear force, which links the proton and neutron within the nucleus, as well as the quarks that compose them. Its carrier is the massless boson called gluon (g). The neutrino, with no electrical charge and with very little mass, interacts with the other three particles by the weak nuclear force. (Figure 13, right) In some way, it also fits the Aristotelian intuition of matter, since, when transforming some nuclear particles in others can produce a transmutation. That is, by varying the number of protons (atomic number) that is what defines a chemical element, one can transform, for example, lead (82) into gold (79) by eliminating two protons from the nucleus of the lead atom.

From our approach, we could risk a summarized standard model, where it becomes evident that the opposing fundamental forces (forms) that affect matter arise from local processes. (Gell-Mann, 2003, p 195) (Figure 14).

Fig. 14. PAU of the standard model

References: no: neutron - p^+ : proton - $d(p^+)$: down quark of the proton - $u(n^0)$: Quark up of the neutron ν^0 : neutrino - γ : photon - g : gluon - w, z, H : bosons

In the previous figure, based on algebra, group theory and symmetry (as in the standard model of particles) we can see the interactions between the four elementary particles that constitute the "heart" of matter: e^- (electron), u (quark up), d (quark down) and ν^0 (neutrino).

The intermediate bosons w and z , which are mediating particles of the weak nuclear interaction, complete the model. They are in charge, in general, to change the taste of other particles. The w -boson intervenes in the β decay in which a neutron becomes a proton and emits an e^- and an antineutrino. While the z -boson intervenes only as a carrier particle of "linear momentum." When two particles exchange a z -boson, one passes the "moment" to the other. This is called "neutral current interaction." None of the particles change the flavor. Finally, the Higgs boson (H) has a fundamental role in the mechanism that originates the mass of elementary particles.

The bosons intervene in everything we know of the universe:

- γ (photon): ontogenetic life (electrochemistry)
- g (gluon): phylogenetic life (sun, light, energy)
- w, z (intermediate): radioactivity
- H (Higgs): transform energy into mass

8.4 Lorentz group

Group theory is the language of symmetries. The Lorentz group is the group of all the Lorentz transformations of Minkowski's four-dimensional space, the classical composition of all non-gravitational physical phenomena. Here we see a simple way to represent a Lorentz group showing its composition, its transformations, and its symmetries. This group shows two symmetries, a continuous (infinitesimal) or rotation and a discrete or reflection. On the other hand, the set of all the transformations of the group is divided into four disjoint subsets, called "pieces." In turn, these "pieces" are linked by three discrete transformations: space-inversion, time-reversal, and total-inversion, so that all can derive from one of them. That is, they constitute a PAU.

Schwichtenberg, J. (2018). Physics from Symmetry. Springer, p. 65.

The basic algebraic operations justify the group dynamics. That is, "arrive" from time to space by means of the two symmetries, using color codes instead of matrices.

9.0 CONCLUSIONS

Analyzing reality from the scientific point of view requires at least three levels be explored: that of the "subjective reality" or of the observer that in this work is postulated as the sustenance and determinant of the other levels, which is based on A belief." The "objective reality" is the level traditionally addressed by science and where you can choose different forms or theories from which to observe and measure the real, which is based on evidence. The "bounded reality" is explored and valued the object of study of an investigation, which is based on experience.

The 'common thread': 'belief → evidence → experience' constitutes, in turn, a PAU that assembles the fundamental elements of all research (Figure 15).

Fig. 15. General PAU of scientific research

Figure 16 summarizes everything analyzed. This scheme shows the dependence between the explored levels of reality. The analysis of objective reality has been carried out from three different proposals: a) The "three worlds of knowledge" of Popper (1993); b) The levels of abstraction of Floridi (2008); and c) From the laws of symmetry of Van Fraassen (1989).

This disposition emphasizes that all research is a dynamic and evolutionary process, in which the subject who investigates and its domain constitute the main axis (∇). However, this is not an impediment for this proposal to be considered, under any aspect, as scientific.

The traditional scientific method, without being obligatory or an absolute guarantee of successful results, depends exclusively on the creative disposition to be carried out. It would be of little use as a method if it were not possible to channel this creativity. The Transcursive Logic, which we could characterize as a "semantic-relational transformation", allows the delimitation of the fundamental elements that intervene in any original approach that is made of reality, so that, after them, the rigorous process can be applied of analysis, organization of available material, ordering and critique of the ideas required by the current methodology so that what is obtained is valid scientific knowledge.

Fig. 16. PAUs of reality analysis
 References: S: subject - O: object - V / T: apparent transformation
 ∇ / T': not apparent transformation - SR: subjective reality
 OR: objective reality - BR: bounded reality

After everything is analyzed, we can say that the interrelationships maintained between the fundamental aspects that define any phenomenon constitutes a "universal pattern" based on a group of transformations.

In this way, we established the foundations of the proposed method:

- a. Find the fundamental elements that characterize a phenomenon.
- b. Depending on a pair of opposing attributions, assign them an operative identity.
- c. With the fundamental elements and the transformations that link them, form an “algebraic group of permutation”, which acts as a “basic dynamic pattern” while ensuring adequate methodological adjustment.
- d. Any transformation that does not belong to the “basic pattern” can be used to transfer to a new system, representative of another phenomenon, the fundamental aspects of known systems, so that, once they conform to the generic pattern, provide us with an explanation of the new phenomenon.

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